

NDAC/LO/010

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WP4100: Location Estimator (Definition)

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1. Principles

The preprocessing of IDT data provides quasi-simultaneous estimates of the phases (and hence grid coordinates) of the fundamental harmonic for the different stars in a frame. The purpose of the Location Estimator is to strengthen these estimates, for single stars, by incorporating also the second harmonic (overtone). This is possible when the phase difference (v_2) between the harmonics is known. The resulting grid coordinate can be regarded as a weighted mean of the coordinates derived from each harmonic separately, with a correction for the known displacement between them.

Before taking the mean it is however necessary to check that the two harmonics give consistent phases and amplitudes. A significant deviation is taken as indication of multiplicity; in such cases the location estimate will be based only on the fundamental harmonic, since this is the more precise component and a mean would not be appropriate.

2. Summary of I/O Data

The relevant Data Interface Descriptions (DID's) are:

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO LOCATION ESTIMATOR
17	IDT Signal Catalogue	• signal parameters and covariances and useful stellar data
18	OTF Data	• smoothed real-time calibrations of modulation coefficients and shifts

DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM LOCATION ESTIMATOR
3	Set Solution	• grid coordinates

3. Method and Basic Equations

Input to the Location Estimator are:

- (i) from the IDT signal catalogue, the estimated signal parameters $\hat{\beta} = (\hat{\beta}_1 \hat{\beta}_2 \hat{\beta}_3 \hat{\beta}_4 \hat{\beta}_5)'$, with estimated covariance $\hat{\Phi}^{-1}$ (or $\hat{\Phi}$, or some equivalent information);
- (ii) from the OTF data file, expected values of $(M_2/M_1)\cos(v_2) = \tilde{\beta}_4$ and $(M_2/M_1)\sin(v_2) = \tilde{\beta}_5$, with covariance $\underline{G}$.

$\tilde{\beta}_4$ and $\tilde{\beta}_5$ are interpolated as functions of time, field coordinates $(\tilde{n}, \tilde{\zeta}, \tilde{f})$, and star colour (BMV); $\underline{G}$ will depend on the same variables and also on the uncertainty of the colour (SDBMV).

The improved estimate of β resulting from combining $\hat{\beta}$ and $\tilde{\beta}$ is simply the weighted mean (A.10.14)

$$\beta^* = (\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1} (\underline{\Phi} \hat{\beta} + \underline{G}^{-1} \tilde{\beta}) \quad (1)$$

$$= \hat{\beta} + (\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1} \underline{G}^{-1} (\tilde{\beta} - \hat{\beta}) \quad (2)$$

Note that only the (2,2)-submatrix at the bottom right corner of $\underline{G}^{-1}$ may be non-zero.

Eqn (2) shows how to compute the "correction" vector

$$\Delta\beta = \beta^* - \hat{\beta} \quad (3)$$

due to the new information $\tilde{\beta}$, $\underline{G}$. The corresponding reduction of the a priori likelihood is

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \Delta\beta' \underline{\Phi} \Delta\beta \quad (4)$$

The single-star hypothesis (H_0) is provisionally rejected if y exceeds some pre-defined limit y_{lim} . An apparent complication here is that the distribution of y (under H_0) depends on the weight ratio between the calibration (of weight $\underline{G}^{-1}$) and observation (of weight $\underline{\Phi}$). This is illustrated by the two extreme cases below.

Case A: If $\underline{G}^{-1} \ll \underline{\Phi}$, we have from (2) $\Delta\beta \approx \underline{0}$ and hence $y \approx 0$. The limiting distribution of y is the delta function.

Case B: If $\underline{G}^{-1} \gg \underline{\Phi}$, the calibration effectively acts as a constraint on β^* . The limiting distribution is therefore χ^2 with 2 degrees of freedom:

$$\Pr[y > \chi^2 \mid H_0, \text{Case B}] \approx \exp(-\chi^2/2) \quad (5)$$

In Case B it is easy to select y_{lim} for any given probability of false detection (e.g. $y_{lim} = 9.2$ for 1 % probability). It seems appropriate however to use the same limit independent of the weight ratio, since $y < y_{lim}$ merely says that β^* is compatible with the observation. Thus H_0 is never rejected in Case A, which is reasonable since the calibration is then not good enough to discriminate between hypotheses.

The improved signal parameters β^* , with covariance $\underline{C}$ and goodness-of-fit measure y , may thus be computed as follows.

- (a) Compute $(\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1}$ and $\underline{G}^{-1}(\tilde{\beta} - \hat{\beta})$. The latter is a 5-vector with only two non-zero elements.
- (b) Compute $\Delta\beta = (\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1} \underline{G}^{-1}(\tilde{\beta} - \hat{\beta})$.
- (c) Compute $y = \frac{1}{2} \Delta\beta' \underline{\Phi} \Delta\beta$.
- (d) If $y < y_{lim}$, put $\beta^* = \hat{\beta} + \Delta\beta$ and $\underline{C} = (\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1}$; otherwise, put $\beta^* = \hat{\beta}$ and $\underline{C} = \underline{\Phi}^{-1}$. The latter relations may be used also if the IC multiplicity parameter (MULT) indicates that the observation should be affected by a companion, even though $y < y_{lim}$.

4. Process Description

The following steps are to be executed.

- (i) Read data for one star in one frame from IDT Signal Catalogue (DID17).
- (ii) Determine whether the observation should be retained (quality check on NACC, NREJ, GOF).
- (iii) Compute $\tilde{\beta}$ and $\underline{G}$ by interpolation in the OTF Data (DID18). The relevant arguments are TMID, IFIELD, ETAA, ZETAA, BMV, and SDBMV. The last one, the colour uncertainty, is introduced by means of

$$\underline{G} = \underline{G}_0(B-V) + \sigma_{B-V}^2 \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}}{\partial (B-V)} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}}{\partial (B-V)} \right)' \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{G}_0$ is the covariance of $\tilde{\beta}$ for a star with accurately known colour.

- (iv) Compute β^* and $\underline{C}$ as in Section 3, (a) - (d).
- (v) Compute the "observed" grid coordinate $G = \beta_3^*/(2\pi)$, with standard deviation $SDG = [(\underline{C})_{33}]^{1/2}/(2\pi)$ and goodness-of-fit parameter $GOFG = \bar{y}$.
- (vi) Output relevant data (DID3).

5. Process Diagram

An updated and improved process diagram is shown on the last page. Completed DID's are indicated with numbers (1 - 18) at the corresponding arrow-heads. A few new symbols are used; their meanings are explained below.

Dashed symbols indicate an optional process. (SMS Update: using positional residuals from the attitude reconstitution to improve the preliminary positions of Star Mapper Stars, SMS. This would eliminate slit errors for most HIPPARCOS stars brighter than $B = 11.$)

NDAC PROCESS DIAGRAM (82.10.25)

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE		DEF	NUM ACC		DIG-ITS
				MIN	MAX		ABS	REL	
DID 3	OUTPUT FROM : LOCATION ESTIMATOR								
	INPUT TO : SET SOLUTION								
		1. For each frame:							
IFRAME	-	frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	-	2
ID (ISTAR)	-	1.1. For ISTAR = 1 to NSTAR: object identification number (0 = unknown; $> 9 \cdot 10^7$ for asteroids)	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
IFIELD (ISTAR)	$(-1)^f$ (p8)	field index (0 = unknown; -1 = FFOV, +1 = PFOV)	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
ETAA (ISTAR)	$\tilde{\eta}$ (p32)	approximate longitud. field coord.	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
ZETAA (ISTAR)	$\tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate transv. field coord.	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
G (ISTAR)	G (p8)	observed grid coordinate	GPGR	-2000	2000	-	10^{-5}	-	9
SDG (ISTAR)	-	standard deviation of G (ISTAR)	GPGR	0	0.9	-	10^{-5}	-	5
GOFG (ISTAR)	-	goodness of fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6

DID 18		OUTPUT FROM : OTF DATA		PAGE : 1 OF 1				
DESIGNATION		INPUT TO : LOCATION ESTIMATOR		DATE : 82.10.25				
ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
	1. <u>For each frame and each star:</u>							
OTF(K), K=1,3	M ₁ etc. (p12)	-	-1	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6
COTF(K,L), K=1,3; L=K,3	- covariance of OTF(K)	-	-1	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6

DID 17		OUTPUT FROM : IDT SIGNAL CATALOGUE				PAGE : 1 OF 1			
INPUT TO : LOCATION ESTIMATOR						DATE : 82.10.25			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL ITS	DIG-
IFRAME	-	1. For each frame: frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_k (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	-	2
ID	-	1.1. For $I = 1$, NSTAR: object identification number	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
BMAG, BMV, SDBMV	-	magnitude, colour, s.d. of colour	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	-	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	-	4
IFIELD	$(-1)^f$ (p8)	field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
ETAA, ZETAA	$\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate field coordinates	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
NACC, NREJ	-	no. of samples accepted/rejected	-	0	9000	0	1	-	4
GOF	-	goodness-of-fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
BETA(K), K=1,5	$\hat{\beta}$ (p29)	estimated signal parameters	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
CBETA(K,L), K=1,5; L=K,5	Φ^{-1} (p29)	covariance of BETA(K) (or equivalent)	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6